

SPIRITUALITY OF AMIR TEMUR AND THE UPBRINGING OF A HEALTHY CHILD

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It is known that our ancestors created a school of great experience in raising a healthy child. After all, our ancestors deeply understood that a healthy child is born only from a physically and spiritually full-fledged person and will benefit society and family in the future.

Our grandfather Amir Timur was a man who could foresee with his mental eyes that he, being comprehensively mature and perfect, would play a huge role in the life of the future generation of the state and society.

He demanded first of all the spiritual and physical health of the parents who would give birth to children. He fought against such harmful vices as drunkenness, smoking, opposed the fact that young people got used to a carefree life, lived without unnecessary hassle and labor, succumbed to vanity and gave birth to lawless children.

The bride considered the choice on a par with state policy.

Special attention in the kingdom was paid to the education of court princes. It is known that for a long time the heads of state breastfed their newborn babies, giving them to a nanny. A pure-bred divorced nanny who was supposed to give birth to a new baby. On the other hand, Atkar was considered the husband of this nanny, and he was considered the father of the prince. Not all were nannies or fathers (atka), but pure-blooded, comprehensively healthy, intelligent, wise people were considered worthy of this job. Timurid babies were called emikdosh.

In addition, such respected Timurid princesses as Bibi-khanim prepared young children for moral knowledge, such as palace rules, behavior, food culture, attention to adults, answers to questions.

Sahibkiran gave his son Shahrukh Mirza, his beloved grandchildren Muhammad Sultan Mirza, Khalil Sultan Mirza, Ulugbek Mirza and other mirzolarians to be raised directly in the brilliant Khanum palace estate.

An example from history: On August 14, 1394, Shahrukh Mirza had a son. His name is Ibrahim Sultan. Prince Tuman agha (the wise head of Amir Temur-Sh.O.) is appointed mentor. "And Amir Usman Abbasni otabek (otalik-Sh.O.), and his wife, a traitor, gave birth to a son Sahibkarang, and became a nurse." At that time, the nobles also tried to raise their children in the hands of special nannies. In our opinion, there are several reasons for this: Firstly, excessive affection, excessive affection, inability to raise boys' children are among the main reasons for this, and secondly, the nobles themselves could rely on the idea that they devote more time to political activities, often because their presence at marches and other trips leads to the fact that the child it's getting out of control. Being somewhat detached from the paternal and maternal love for the comprehensive hardening of the child, the Child took on the upbringing of his mentors without too much resistance. Dozens of shahu generals, poets

and scientists who grew up inside the Timurids testify that great attention was paid to the upbringing of a healthy child in the kingdom.

The children of the nobility from the age of 4-5 acquired knowledge of theology and morality. At that time there were two types of madrasas. The first were madrasas providing education, and the second were madrasas providing higher education. In these educational institutions, along with theology, Law (Fiqh), logic, mathematics (mathematics), geometry (Handasa), falakiyat (science), medicine, geography, Arabic and other subjects were taught.

The princes, young children who started studying at the madrasah, were told stories and fairy tales of various educational significance by storytellers, and they formed feelings of striving for good, hatred for evil.

Historical science flourished during the lifetime of Amir Temur. The very life and work of Amir Timur were marked by heroism.

The Timurids were the founders of the scientific environment of that time and showed high spiritual courage in our national history. Timurid managed to awaken a passion for science in the minds of young people, becoming a personal example for the people of kings and princes. These are epic heroes who have given boot power to the wheels of our national history.

In particular, the palace known as the palace of Princess Bibikhanum, with the permission of Emir Timur, built the Bibikhanum madrasah at his own expense, and hundreds of mature young generations of his time were formed in this place, who played an important role in the spiritual life of the country.

Ulugbek Mirza was not only a great astronomer and mathematician, but also a leading expert in Arabic and Persian languages of his time, a musician and a historian. This indicates that the Timurids were not limited only to in-depth study of one or two areas, that along with the Temurian kings and princes, the Talibs of science at that time were leading scientists in the east, they knew other areas perfectly well.

Ulugbek personally built four madrasas that enjoyed great prestige in the most influential east of that time: one in Bukhara and Gijduvan and two in Samarkand. During this period, Khanum madrasahs, Kutdibbin Sadr, and Muhammad Sultan also operated in Samarkand.

In these madrasas, young people gained knowledge and became versatile mature specialists. Mirza Ulugbek continued the good deeds of his grandfather as the fruit of the tree of knowledge grown by Amir Temur. Amir Timur and his successors marked the beginning of an important rise in the history of raising a healthy generation.

Special attention should be paid to one aspect: only from among the Timurids at the same time, generals, scientists, historians and poets grew up in the person of the ruler - in particular, many encyclopedic scientists, such as Mirza Ulugbek, Shahrukh Mirza, Hussein Boykara, Babur Mirza. The great discoveries of the Timurids also testify to their high spirituality and spiritual courage, that special attention was paid to the upbringing of a healthy child in the kingdom. Ulugbek Academy, Herat School, Baysungur Academy are also the product of knowledge provided to young children, Amir Temur's policy regarding a healthy child. Timurid kings and princes, as a rule, madrasah students, at one time Greco-Roman scientists, were aware of the latest discoveries of the East and West and strengthened their knowledge by developing them and laying the cornerstones of the Timurid Renaissance in the East.

Sahibkiran, his sons, grandsons, military leaders and the warriors themselves were originally Bahadur, brave people, epic heroes.

The growth of interest in science under Amir Temur and the Timurids contributed to the general rise of spiritual culture, the growth of production and crafts. At that time, the rapid development of irrigation, urban planning, architecture gave impetus to the development of various directions in science.

The School of Craftsmen was also considered an important school in teaching children the craft. There the children overcame any difficult difficulties, mastered new knowledge and skills, became masters of their time. The House of Masters was a large pedagogical school that taught young people hard work, honesty, the value of man and work.

Physical education was considered one of the most important foundations of raising a healthy child during the reign of Amir Temur. At that time, folk games were spread all over the country, and young children regularly played sports with these games. Many young officers and Navarrese of the 200,000 soldiers who participated in the campaigns of Amir Timur became masters of sports of their time. Under Amir Timur, sports and military exercises complemented each other. In the Middle Ages, when wars were the main thing, the requirement of that time was that every person was left-handed, physically hardy, had knowledge and skills capable of resisting the enemy under any circumstances.

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